

STRATEGIES FOR THE USE OF MASS MEDIA IN POLITICAL CAMPAIGNS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the dual function of mass media as a means of enhancing the political culture of the population and as a mechanism for organizing political pressure. It is highlighted that in the context of the expanding information space and the development of digital technologies, the media, while serving as an important factor in shaping political consciousness and civic activity, can also become a tool for targeted influence by various political forces. The study scientifically substantiates theories of political communication, media influence strategies, and their impact on socio-political stability. Additionally, recommendations are provided on optimizing media participation in political processes and strengthening democratic principles.

Keywords; Mass media, strategy, civil society, information policy, public opinion, media literacy, information security, social influence, information and communication technologies.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ommaviy axborot vositalarining aholining siyosiy madaniyatini oshirish vositasi hamda siyosiy bosimni tashkil etish mexanizmi sifatidagi ikki qirralik funksiyasi tahlil qilinadi. Axborot maydonining kengayishi va raqamli texnologiyalar rivoji sharoitida OAV siyosiy ong va fuqarolik faolligini shakllantirishning muhim omili bo'lib xizmat qilishi bilan birga, turli siyosiy kuchlar tomonidan maqsadli ta'sir o'tkazish vositasiga ham aylanishi mumkinligi yoritilgan. Tadqiqotda siyosiy kommunikatsiya nazariyalari, media ta'sir strategiyalari va ularning ijtimoiy-siyosiy barqarorlikka ta'siri ilmiy jihatdan asoslab beriladi. Shuningdek, OAVning siyosiy jarayonlardagi ishtirokini optimallashtirish va demokratik tamoyillarni mustahkamlash bo'yicha tavsiyalar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar; Ommaviy axborot vositalari, strategiya, fuqarolik jamiyati, axborot siyosati, jamoatchilik fikri, media savodxonlik, axborot xavfsizligi, ijtimoiy ta'sir, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется двойственная функция средств массовой информации как средства повышения политической культуры населения и механизма организации политического давления. Освещено, что в условиях расширения информационного пространства и развития цифровых технологий СМИ могут служить важным фактором формирования политического сознания и гражданской активности, а также стать средством целенаправленного воздействия различных политических сил. В исследовании научно обоснованы теории политической коммуникации, стратегии влияния СМИ и их влияние на социально-политическую стабильность. Также даны рекомендации по оптимизации участия СМИ в политических процессах, укреплению демократических принципов.

Ключевые слова; СМИ, стратегия, гражданское общество, информационная политика, общественное мнение, медиаграмотность, информационная безопасность, социальное воздействие, информационно-коммуникационные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

Current socio-economic problems are widely reflected in public opinion surveys on various thematic areas. However, modern political television programs often give priority to covering foreign political events, distracting public attention and influencing political consciousness. In this context, the media serve not only as a means of setting the political agenda, but also as a means of mobilization. Recent developments indicate an increased focus of the media on the activities of state and political leaders, in particular the president, the head of government, members of the cabinet and parliament, while certain destabilizing forces have used the media to stimulate public participation in political actions such as rallies. Accordingly, any study of the role of the media in shaping political worldviews requires a careful analysis of trust in the media.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a comprehensive set of scholarly methods, including historical and logical analysis, analytical and synthetic approaches, content analysis, a systematic framework, and observation. These methodological tools facilitated a consistent and objective examination of the developmental stages of mass media, its content, and its functional role within society.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Given that mass media outlets often seek to maximize profit and can be easily influenced by governing authorities, the level of trust in the information they disseminate should be expected to remain low. However, survey results indicate that more than half of respondents approve of the activities of mass media. At the same time, 40 percent of respondents express confidence in their own impartiality. Notably, among individuals aged 18 to 30, trust in mass media is lower: only 39 percent report trusting it, while 50 percent express distrust.

The indicated distrust is linked to the unreliability of the information provided, making it easy to question its veracity. Furthermore, in the political sphere, “various

scandals and pseudo-events are often employed to divert public attention from any serious societal issues”[1;85].

Summarizing the above, it can be stated with confidence that if a society seeks to follow the path of progress, it must pay close attention to what is being shown to it, what it is learning, and what it is reading. Otherwise, societal decline becomes inevitable, and a fertile ground for the manipulation of public consciousness will constantly emerge and solidify.

Mass media contribute to assessing the opinions and activities of social institutions (including those in power) and public officials in fulfilling their responsibilities to society. Among the most important functions of mass media is the formation of public consciousness—whether ideological or socially oriented—which encompasses a wide scope of influence: from reporting facts and events, to shaping public opinion, and further to influencing people’s values, ideals, and worldviews.

In summary, it can be asserted with confidence that if a society aims to progress on the path of development, it must pay close attention to what is presented to it, what it learns, and what it studies. Otherwise, societal decline becomes inevitable, and fertile ground for the manipulation of public consciousness constantly emerges and solidifies.

Mass media contribute to the evaluation of the reflections and activities of social institutions (including those in power) and officials regarding their responsibilities before society. Among the most important functions of mass media is the function of shaping public consciousness (whether ideological or socially oriented), encompassing a broad scope of influence — from reporting facts and events, influencing public opinion, to affecting individuals’ values, ideals, and worldviews” [1;88].

The role of mass media becomes particularly evident in relation to the level of civil society. Thus, “the following functions of mass media in relation to society and the political system can be distinguished:

Information:

- ✓ Providing information about events and circumstances occurring in society and the world;
- ✓ Supplying information to support innovation processes.
 - **Social Communication:**
- ✓ Interpreting and explaining ongoing events;
- ✓ Supporting existing norms and power relations;
- ✓ Facilitating socialization;
- ✓ Coordinating multifaceted social activities and shaping public consent.
 - **Ensuring Continuity:**

- ✓ Representing dominant cultural models, recognizing subcultures, and new cultural trends;
- ✓ Preserving common social values.
 - **Recreational (Restorative) Function:**
- ✓ Creating opportunities for leisure and entertainment;
- ✓ Reducing social tensions.
 - **Mobilization:**
- ✓ Organizing campaigns related to urgent political, economic, and social objectives” [2;110].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the concept of the functions of mass media has evolved because the subject itself has changed. In a modern, information-rich society, mass media play an incomparably more significant role than they did in the first half of the previous century. Initially emerging to satisfy people's needs for information and communication, mass media have become an integral part of human life. They provide information, conduct analysis, shape the worldview, and offer entertainment.

Reference:

1. Прохоров Е. П. Введение в журналистику / Е.П.Прохоров.- М.: Высш. шк., 1988. С. 50–130.
2. Филиппов С. СМИ как механизм формирования гражданского общества в переходных системах //Власть. — 2002. — № 8. — С. 110.
3. Эшбеков Б. Особенности СМИ в повышении социальной активности граждан в Новом Узбекистане //Общество и инновации. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 80-88.
4. Эшбеков Б. Н. СИЁСИЙ ОНГ ТУШУНЧАСИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ТАРИХИ ВА ЖАҲОН ҲАМЖАМИЯТИДАГИ АҲАМИЯТИ //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 24. – С. 11-15.
5. Жўраев Н. History is a philosophy of a human, time and place // Иностранные языки в Узбекистане. – 2017. – №. 3. – С. 212-225.
6. Jo'rayev N. Tarix falsafasining nazariy asoslari //Т.:“Ma'naviyat. – 2008.
7. Усанов Р. Т., Хаккулов Н. К. ИЗ ИСТОРИИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ПРОБЛЕМЫ «НЕНАСИЛИЕ» //Экономика и социум. – 2024. – №. 6-2 (121). – С. 1406-1413.
8. ХАККУЛОВ Н. К., РИЗАЕВ И. И. Цифровая культура и неприкосновенность личности //Новые технологии в учебном процессе и производстве. – 2023. – С. 605-606.
9. Ризаев И. И., Хаккулов Н. К. Влияние цифровой культуры на неприкосновенность жизни человека в обществе //Оргкомитет. – 2023. – С. 342.